

Transport Mobility Management

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Traffic congestion is a growing problem in urban areas all over the world. Traffic planners in city administration are usually dealing with this problem by deciding to construct new infrastructure or extending existing public transport network. However, this approach can lead to longer trip distances or even more trips per user. This is by experts called induced traffic. Another conventional option is land-use and infrastructure coordination which is implemented in the Copenhagen planning area as the principal of proximity to train stations for all intensive land uses. Mobility Management may be a new approach or tool that can help reduce the negative impacts of the traffic. The initiatives are either informing about transport alternatives or providing incentives for more sustainable transport. Green Mobility Management is already applied by many Danish municipalities.

The Mobility Management initiatives can be in different categories such as public transportation, bike and pedestrian transportation, optimized use- and reduced need of transport. The initiatives help informing the traffic users about the alternative modes of transport, possibilities for attending a Green-driving course or suggest the possibilities for home working days, phone/video-meetings or carpooling.

The project analyzes data provided by Formel M project that has developed and applied Mobility Management initiatives in Danish workplaces (private companies, city halls and hospitals). We focus on 28 workplaces that participated in Formel M including before and after surveys of employees travel behaviors. The companies are all located in The Capital Region of Denmark. We analyze the so called "treatment effect" aiming to find out if the Formel M initiatives had a significant effect on the employees mode choice and thus the degree to which mobility management can be effective in shaping travel outcomes.

The results show that the effects of mobility management are higher for workplaces located far away from train stations (1,200 m) compared to the companies located close to a station (600 m). This indicates how mobility management can be supplementary to existing land-use/infrastructure coordination policies.

The causes of the treatment effect have also been investigated. It can be concluded that simple initiatives such as selling tickets for public transport at the workplace makes the possibility for using public transport among the employees higher. The durability of the 'mobility management effect' is an obvious question, but cannot be answered within the project.